

The OpenMMPol Library for Polarizable QM/MM Calculations of Properties and Dynamics

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We present a new library designed to provide a simple and straightforward way to implement QM/AMOEBA and other polarizable QM/MM methods based on induced point dipoles. The library, herein referred to as OpenMMPol, is free and open-sourced and is engineered to address the increasing demand for accurate and efficient QM/MM simulations. OpenMMPol is specifically designed to allow polarizable QM/MM calculations of ground state energies and gradients, and excitation properties. Key features of OpenMMPol include a modular architecture facilitating extensibility, parallel computing capabilities for enhanced performance on modern cluster architectures, and a user-friendly interface for intuitive implementation and a simple and flexible structure for providing input data. To show the capabilities offered by the library we present an interface with PySCF to perform QM/AMOEBA molecular dynamics, geometry optimization and excited state calculation based on (TD)DFT.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, hybrid models which combine a quantum chemical description with a classical but atomistic model based on molecular mechanics (MM) force fields have gained significant popularity for elucidating properties and processes of embedded molecules. QM/MM methods have shown to be extremely effective in describing not only homogeneous solvents but also much more complex environments characterized by extensive inhomogeneity and anisotropy.^{1,2} Notably, these methods enable the explicit incorporation of electrostatic effects from the embedding environment into the QM description of electronic density, when utilizing the electrostatic embedding formulation. The escalating popularity of QM/MM methods is further fueled by their ease of implementation in electronic structure codes. Specifically, incorporating the electrostatic influence of a group of MM atoms on the description of the QM charge density simply necessitates expanding the classical charges from the molecular nuclei to supplementary points situated outside the QM subsystem. This means that the the only part of the QM Hamiltonian which has to be changed is the one calculating the electrostatic potential of the nuclei.

Beyond the electrostatic embedding approach, QM/MM methods offer more comprehensive formulations. Specifically, leveraging a polarizable MM force field enables the integration of mutual polarization effects between the QM and MM subsystems. This can be achieved in different ways, including fluctuating charges³⁻⁸, Drude oscillators⁹⁻¹², or induced point dipoles (IPD)¹³⁻²⁷. In this contribution, we focus on the IPD approach. Within this framework, each MM atom not only carries a fixed point charge but also possesses a typically isotropic polarizability. This property enables MM atoms to respond to applied electric fields by generating atomic induced dipoles. When these polarizable MM atoms embed a QM subsystem the field they experience arises from both the QM charge and the MM charges. The resulting induced dipoles introduce a new term in the QM Hamiltonian which, this time, depends on the QM charge density. As a result, the solution of the new Hamiltonian will correspond to QM and MM systems which have been mutually polarized. A popular example of the IPD formulation of polarizable embedding QM/MM is the one based on the AMOEBA force field.²⁸ In the AMOEBA framework, each MM atom is additionally characterized by fixed multipoles extending up to quadrupoles.

The integration of mutual polarization alongside fixed-charge electrostatic effects is ex-

pected to enrich the description of environmental effects on molecular processes, especially when these processes involve multiple electronic states.^{29,30} Nevertheless, while this enriched model offers increased comprehensiveness, it also introduces additional computational challenges. The appearance of a new QM-density-dependent term in the Hamiltonian in fact significantly increases the complexity with respect to the standard electrostatic embedding formulation. As a result, the implementation of polarizable QM/MM methods in electronic structure codes is far from being straightforward. This complexity is further amplified when the focus extends beyond calculating the energy of the QM subsystem to encompass molecular properties, such as geometries, or dynamic processes. In all these cases in fact it is necessary to extend the polarizable QM/MM method to analytical gradients.

IPD based polarizable QM/MM implementations are available in both commercial and open source quantum chemistry suite of programs. Our QM/MMPol and QM/AMOEBA machinery has been originally implemented into a development version of Gaussian.^{20,21,31} A similar approach based on the AMOEBA force field has also been implemented in the linear-scaling code OneTEP³², which has been interfaced to Tinker³³ via the TINKTEP interface.²³ IPD Polarizable QM/MM calculations are also available in deMon2K.^{27,34} However, the most commonly available model is the Polarizable Embedding model^{22,30}, which has been implemented in two open-source libraries, PELib^{22,30} and CPPE^{35,36}, which have in turn been interfaced with various commercial and opensource quantum chemistry packages.

Our aim in developing OpenMMPol is to provide a flexible yet powerful platform to use the current state-of-the art atomistic polarizable force field in combination with virtually every QM method already implemented in any electronic structure code. Moreover, we would like to have, as much as possible, a clear and easy-to-understand implementation to allow using this framework as a development platform for new features. An important feature, and element of novelty, contained in OpenMMPol is that it provides all the features required to perform ab-initio, polarizable QM/MM MD simulations, as it includes all the bonded, non-bonded and QM/MM contributions to not only the energy, but also its gradients, including with respect the positions of the MM atoms. In other words, OpenMMPol contains a decade of developments carried out by our group towards general and efficient multiscale strategies to study molecular properties and dynamics.³⁷

II. THE OPENMMPOL LIBRARY

OpenMMPol is built as a library that offers interfaces to the most popular language used in computational chemistry (C/C++, Python and Fortran). This design allows using the library in combination with most QM codes with a minimal impact on the build system and on the code itself. The interfaces exposed are as much as possible consistent between the different languages, with some adaptation to make their usage as natural as possible from each language.

The code, available on GitHub repository <https://github.com/Molecolab-Pisa/OpenMMPol>, is written in modern Fortran, strictly adhering to the 2008ts standard and can therefore be compiled using different compilers suites; in particular GNU, Intel and NVidia compiler builds are tested using a continuous integration pipelines. The code is compiled using the popular and flexible CMake build system and only requires few external libraries (namely BLAS LAPACK, OpenMP, OpenSSL, cJSON, and optionally HDF5 and PyBind11) which are mature, stable and available on most Linux systems.

To interface a QM code with the OpenMMPol library, the host code should be written in Fortran, C/C++, or Python and it should be able to compute electrostatic potential and electric field one-electron integrals. To exploit all the features offered by OpenMMPol, and in particular to compute QM/AMOEBA energies and forces, field gradient and field hessian integrals should be available as well (*vide infra*). When higher/arbitrary order (*e.g.* electric-field gradients) integrals are not readily available, they can be always computed by numerical differentiation of lower-order integrals that are available in most codes.

Internally, OpenMMPol is organized in several Fortran modules which are opaque to the final users. A single interface Fortran module (or an equivalent C library or Python module) exposes to the user all the functions, constants, and data structures required for interfacing an external QM code; as a convention, all the objects contained in the interface module have a name beginning with `ommp_`. The code is documented using FORD, which allows one to generate HTML doc pages directly from the comments in the code.

In the following sections we show the code's capabilities and the basics of the underlying implemented equations.

A. Input and Data Structures

The code is built around a main object called `ommp_system` that represents the current status of the MM part of the system, together with all the parameters (electrostatics, dispersion-repulsion/van der Waals and bonded). Such object is a derived type in Fortran and is handled as a `void` pointer in C, and an actual object in Python. The library offers different options to initialize those objects from different file formats:

- `.hdf5` this is a standard binary file format, which has been used to package all the information contained in the `ommp_system` object for easy loading and saving. It has the advantage of being a binary file whose I/O can be easily parallelized. At the same time, since it is a widespread format in computational sciences, several applications and libraries allowing an easy inspection/modification of this format are available.
- `.xyz + .prm` according to Tinker manual specifications; this format is intended to be used for AMOEBA or other force fields implemented in both Tinker and OpenMMPol; currently is a good choice as it allows using the Tinker infrastructure to prepare input files and then use it for QM/MM calculations with any QM code exploiting the OpenMMPol capabilities.
- `.mmp` a formatted file format containing only electrostatic and topological information about the system. It was developed and used in our group in earlier development phases of QM/MMPol methods and is implemented here for backward compatibility. As it cannot contain information about van der Waals (vdW) terms and bonded ones, it cannot be used for the calculation of the full gradients for QM/MM systems. This format is described in the Supplementary Material.

To facilitate the interface with a QM code, a second object, called `ommp_qm_helper` is provided. This object represents the QM system within the library and is initialized using the coordinates and atomic numbers of the atoms of the QM subsystem. If required, a parameter file (in Tinker format) and atom types can also be assigned. This object is typically used to compute various electrostatic properties (potential, field, field gradient and Hessian) of the nuclei at the MM sites, the QM-MM component of the vdW interactions, and all the operations related to link atoms. Again, when the geometry of the QM system

is altered (eg. during a geometry optimization, an MD simulation), the host code should also update the corresponding `ommp_qm_helper` object.

In order to make the modification of the input section of the host code as limited as possible, we have encapsulated all the OpenMMPol-related parameters in a single JSON file that is the only input required to initialize the library. In this file each possible option for a run (*e.g.* input files, options for solving the linear system, required version of OpenMMPol, etc.) can be specified. A single interface call (`ommp_smartinput`) does all the checks on both the JSON file and the file used to initialize the `ommp_system` object; this interface routine sets all the relevant parameters and returns an `ommp_system` object, and, if needed, an `ommp_qm_helper` object. This approach is beneficial when accessing all the functionality provided by the library (*e.g.* QM/MM systems with link atoms) with a standard input file that can be used across different QM software packages interfaced to OpenMMPol. Moreover the use of a standard input format such as JSON allows either easy generation of inputs from scripts and modification by hand.

Even if lower-level initialization routines are available through the interface, we discourage their direct use as they are all accessible through `ommp_smartinput` and a properly configured JSON file that also triggers several checks on the input that should otherwise be re-implemented in the host code. The parsing of JSON input relies on a small portion of code written in C99 exploiting the cJSON library, and interfaced to Fortran.

For a more detailed and technical reference of the internal structure of classes and modules implemented by OpenMMPol, we advise the reader to refer to the documentation provided at the official git repository (<https://molecolab-pisa.github.io/OpenMMPol/>).

In the following, we briefly recapitulate the main equations implemented in OpenMMPol. We use the following notation conventions. Sums over cartesian components (*e.g.*, x, y, z for position vectors or dipoles, xx, xy, xz, \dots for quadrupoles and so one) are implicit and not shown. We use bold symbols for vectors and matrices that are collections of quantities, *e.g.*, \mathbf{q} is a vector that collects all the point charges q_i on MM atoms, or that are whole QM matrices, *e.g.*, \mathbf{P} is the density matrix of the systems, the elements of which are $P_{\mu\nu}$.

B. Electrostatics and polarization

OpenMMPol is primarily conceived to allow QM/MM calculations with polarizable MM models based on the induced point dipoles (IPD) formalism. Two distinct cases are addressed by the library: the AMBER polarizable force field¹⁹, which closely resembles a standard AMBER FF with additional polarizabilities, and the AMOEBA force field^{28,38}. The latter differs from the former in two main aspects: first, the fixed part of electrostatics on each MM atom is represented with a multipolar expansion up to quadrupoles rather than just a point charge. The second difference, which is addressed more in detail in the last part of this Section, consists in a different definition for the electric field generated by the fixed multipoles used to *induce* the dipoles, and the one used to compute the interaction with the induced dipoles.

The presence of fixed multipoles on MM atoms implicitly poses a further complication: since dipoles and quadrupoles are vector quantities, in order to give a physically sound description of an atom's electric field, they should rotate together with the molecule. AMOEBA implements this by parametrizing dipoles and quadrupoles in an absolute reference frame and then rotating according to some parametrized rules to get them in the correct position for a particular geometry of the molecule.³⁹ In the following, unless explicitly stated, we always refer to the rotated multipoles.

OpenMMPol is able to compute all the energy and derivative terms related to electrostatics and polarization needed for a full QM/MM gradient calculation. Currently, we have implemented all the electrostatic and polarization terms using standard double loops that exhibit a $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ scaling, including the solution to the polarization equations which is done using a preconditioned conjugate gradient iterative solver. We note that the scaling can be reduced to $\mathcal{O}(N)$ by using the fast multipoles method (FMM)³¹ to compute all such terms. A linear-scaling implementation will be distributed with the next release of OpenMMPol.

For the fixed electrostatic part, three interface functions are available:

- `ommp_get_fixedelec_energy` computes the interaction energy between the fixed charges (or multipoles, for AMOEBA) on each MM atom, according to

$$\mathcal{E}^{\text{MM-elec}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} s_{ij} \sum_{L_1} \sum_{L_2} M_i^{L_1} T_{ij}^{L_1 L_2} M_j^{L_2}, \quad (1)$$

where indices i and j refer to MM atoms whereas indices L_x refer to angular momenta

(0 for charges, 1 for dipoles, and so on). s_{ij} is a scaling factor which accounts for the exclusion of neighbour electrostatics, $M_k^{L_x}$ is a Cartesian multipole centered on atom k with angular momentum L_x . The components of the interaction matrix $T_{ij}^{L_1 L_2}$ are defined as follows¹⁵,

$$[T_{ij}^{L_1 L_2}]_{\alpha' \beta' \dots}^{\alpha \beta \dots} = \frac{\partial^{L_1}}{\partial r_i^\alpha \partial r_i^\beta \dots} \frac{\partial^{L_2}}{\partial r_j^{\alpha'} \partial r_j^{\beta'} \dots} \frac{1}{|r_i - r_j|}. \quad (2)$$

We note that for the AMBER FF the angular momentum assumes only the value of zero, while for AMOEBA it ranges from zero to two, *i.e.* up to quadrupoles.

- `ommp_fixedelec_geomgrad` computes the derivative of the interaction energy between fixed charges (or multipoles) with respect to the displacement of each MM atom. The implemented expression can be derived by differentiating Eq. (1) with respect to the position of a MM atom k and reads

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{\text{MM-elec}}}{\partial r_{k,\text{MM}}} = \sum_{j \neq k} s_{kj} \sum_{L_1} \sum_{L_2} M_k^{L_1} T_{kj}^{L_1+1 L_2} M_j^{L_2} \quad (3)$$

- `ommp_potential_mm2ext` and `ommp_field_mm2ext` are used to compute the electrostatic potential and electric field respectively, generated by MM atoms at a set of arbitrary “external” coordinates; *i.e.*,

$$\Phi_i^L = (-1)^L \sum_{j \neq i} \sum_{L_2} T_{ij}^{L L_2} M_j^{L_2}, \quad (4)$$

where $L = 0$ for the potential, $L = 1$ for the electric field, and so on.

In both AMBER and AMOEBA, each MM atom is further endowed with an isotropic polarizability α_i . As a response to the electric field generated by both the QM and the MM parts of the system, an induced point dipole is generated on each atom. The induced dipoles are obtained as the solution to the following linear system of equations

$$\alpha_i^{-1} \mu_i + \sum_{j \neq i} s_{ij}^\mu \mathcal{T}_{ij}^{11} \mu_j = E_i^{\text{MM}} + E_i^{\text{QM}}, \quad (5)$$

whose right-hand-side contains the electric fields E_i^{MM} generated by the fixed multipoles and E_i^{QM} generated by the QM density. In Eq. 5, we have introduced a screening factor s_{ij}^μ that accounts for excluded interactions (*i.e.*, for bonded atoms, or atoms belonging to the

same polarization group depending on the force field) and the damped interaction matrix (\mathcal{T}_{ij})¹⁵, defined as in Eq. 2 but replacing the standard Coulomb Kernel with $\lambda(r_{ij})/|r_i - r_j|$. The damping function^{15,19,40,41} λ ensures that, when the distance between two polarizable sites becomes small, the interaction energy does not diverge, as the kernel has a finite zero distance limit, avoiding thus the so-called *polarization catastrophe*. We also underline that the screening factor used to compute E_i^{MM} in Eq. 5 could differ from the one used in Eq. 1.

Equations 5 can be collected in a matrix form, by introducing the $3n \times 3n$ matrix \mathbf{T} , whose 3×3 blocks are defined as follows

$$T_{ij} = \alpha_i^{-1} \delta_{ij} + (1 - \delta_{ij}) \mathcal{T}_{ij}^{11}, \quad (6)$$

where δ is the Kronecker delta. The resulting linear system reads

$$\mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu} = \mathbf{E}^{\text{MM}} + \mathbf{E}^{\text{QM}} \quad (7)$$

and is solved by calling the OpenMMPol function `set_external_field`, which requires as input the QM electric field (\mathbf{E}^{QM}) calculated at the polarizable atom positions. For a standard IDP-based force field, like AMBER, the polarization energy can thus be written as

$$\mathcal{E}^{\text{Pol}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \mu_i \left(E_i^{\text{MM}} + E_i^{\text{QM}} \right). \quad (8)$$

In the case of AMOEBA force field, the problem is slightly more involved because the electric field that induces the dipoles is computed according to different screening rules with respect to the one used to compute the interaction energy.^{28,41,42} Across the code, and in the present paper, the first field is called *direct* (\mathbf{E}_d) and the second one *polarization* (\mathbf{E}_p).

To deal with this specificity, the following polarization Lagrangian has been proposed^{43,44}

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\mu}^d, \boldsymbol{\mu}^p) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \mu_i^d \left(E_i^{\text{MM},p} + E_i^{\text{QM}} \right) + \sum_i \mu_i^p \left((\mathbf{T}\boldsymbol{\mu}^d)_i - E_i^{\text{MM},d} - E_i^{\text{QM}} \right) \quad (9)$$

where a new set of induced dipoles, $\boldsymbol{\mu}^p$, act as Lagrange multipliers to enforce that the IPDs $\boldsymbol{\mu}^d$ satisfy the polarization equation. By imposing the stationarity of the Lagrangian with respect to both dipoles, we get two linear systems of equations of the type 7, one referring to $\boldsymbol{\mu}^p$ and the other to $\boldsymbol{\mu}^d$ respectively. The polarization energy for AMOEBA thus reads:

$$\mathcal{E}^{\text{Pol}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \mu_i^d \left(E_i^{\text{MM},p} + E_i^{\text{QM}} \right). \quad (10)$$

C. Nonelectrostatic terms

Even if nonelectrostatic terms do not enter directly in the QM electronic Hamiltonian, they should not be overlooked, as they are essential to perform MD and geometry optimizations. OpenMMPol is able to compute all bonded and non-bonded non-electrostatic terms needed to perform calculations with AMOEBA and AMBER force fields.

Among the non-electrostatic terms a special attention is devoted to the implementation of the vdW interaction which is present in every pair of atoms and therefore it is $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ scaling if implemented with a naïve double loop strategy. In our code, two slightly different expressions for this interaction are implemented: the 6-12 Lennard-Jones used in AMBER⁴⁵

$$\mathcal{E}_{i,j}^{\text{vdW}} = \epsilon_{i,j} \left[\left(\frac{R_{ij}^0}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - 2 \left(\frac{R_{ij}^0}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right], \quad (11)$$

and the buffered 7-14 Lennard-Jones used for the AMOEBA forcefield²⁸:

$$\mathcal{E}_{ij}^{\text{vdW}} = \epsilon_{ij} \left(\frac{1 + \delta}{\rho_{ij} + \delta} \right)^7 \left(\frac{1 + \gamma}{\rho_{ij}^7 + \gamma} - 2 \right), \quad (12)$$

where $\rho_{ij} = r_{ij}/R_{ij}^0$, and δ and γ are fixed values equal to 0.07 and 0.12, respectively.⁴² Independently of the model, VdW interactions decay very fast at long distances. Due to this characteristic, the calculation of VdW interaction energy can be approximated using a simple cutoff distance and calculated in a linear scaling computation time. To get the desired linear scaling we used an improved variation of the cell-lists algorithm⁴⁶. To minimize the memory footprint, the cell lists themselves, i.e., the lists of particles contained in each cell in which the simulation space is divided, are saved in a compressed format similar to the Yale format for sparse matrices. The current implementation only allows to use a *hard* cutoff without any smearing function. The exact value of this cutoff distance can be set in the JSON input file by the user. If no cutoff is specified here, the $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ algorithm is used. The interface functions available for VdW are:

- `ommp_get_vdw_energy` and `ommp_qm_helper_vdw_energy` are used to compute the VdW energy of the MM part and of the QM-MM interaction.
- `ommp_get_vdw_geomgrad` and `ommp_qm_helper_vdw_geomgrad` are used to compute the derivatives of the energy terms above with respect to the coordinates of the nuclei. While the first term has only contributions on MM atoms, the second one has contributions on both QM and MM atoms.

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PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0198251

The bonded terms are very numerous, but they are generally inexpensive to compute, exhibit a naturally linear scaling and are very similar across force fields. To keep this section concise we will only resume the energy terms implemented in OpenMMPol with the corresponding functions.

Energy term	Potential function	Expression
bond stretching	<code>ommp_get_bond_energy</code>	$k\Delta l^2(1 + k_3\Delta l + k_4\Delta l^2)$
Urey-Bradley angle	<code>ommp_get_urey_energy</code>	$k\Delta l^2(1 + k_3\Delta l + k_4\Delta l^2)$
angle bending	<code>ommp_get_angle_energy</code>	$k\Delta\theta^2(1 + \sum_{i=1}^4 k_{i+2}\Delta\theta^i)$
out-of-plane bending	<code>ommp_get_opb_energy</code>	$k\Delta\theta^2(1 + \sum_{i=1}^4 k_{i+2}\Delta\theta^i)$
π -torsion	<code>ommp_get_pitors_energy</code>	$k(1 + \cos(2\theta - \pi))$
dihedral torsion	<code>ommp_get_torsion_energy</code>	$\sum_{i=1,6} A_i(1 + \cos(i\theta - \phi_i))$
improper torsion	<code>ommp_get_imptorsion_energy</code>	$\sum_{i=1,3} A_i(1 + \cos(i\theta - \phi_i))$
stretching-bending coupling	<code>ommp_get_strbnd_energy</code>	–
stretching-torsion coupling	<code>ommp_get_strtor_energy</code>	–
bending-torsion coupling	<code>ommp_get_angtor_energy</code>	–
torsion-torsion cmap	<code>ommp_get_tortor_energy</code>	–

TABLE I. Bonded energy terms implemented in OpenMMPol, name of functions needed to compute the energy terms and implemented potential functions. In general Δl represents a length variation with respect to a reference length, $\Delta\theta$ an angle variation with respect to a reference angle, and θ are angles. All the other terms are parameters.

All the derivatives of those terms are also implemented in OpenMMPol and are readily available through interface functions that are completely analogous to the ones listed in Table I.

D. Link Atoms

OpenMMPol implements link atoms to treat systems with a covalent bond across the QM and MM parts of the system. To use link atoms, in the JSON inputs the user should specify the atom type for every atom in the QM system, and the atoms involved in the bond to be cut. In practice the link atoms should be explicitly present in the QM part of the system; their coordinates are irrelevant as OpenMMPol automatically displace them in the correct position as soon as the calculation starts. In the present implementation the link atom position is determined by:

$$r_{\text{LA}} = r_{\text{QM}} + d_{\text{LA}} \frac{r_{\text{QM}} - r_{\text{MM}}}{|r_{\text{QM}} - r_{\text{MM}}|}. \quad (13)$$

The parameter d_{LA} has a default value of 1.1 Å which can be modified through the JSON input file. The interactions in the link atom region are treated using the following rules⁴⁷:

- the stretching term, the bending terms and the torsion terms involving the QM and the MM atoms are added according to FF rules,
- QM-MM VdW interactions are screened according to FF rules and neglected for the link atom,
- Fixed electrostatic multipoles and polarizabilities are removed from the MM atom involved in the bond with the QM atom, as well as on every atom within two bonds from it (if needed the distance can be increased to an arbitrary number of bonds through JSON input),
- Charges are removed from the linked MM atom and its neighbours and they are redistributed evenly on the first unaffected neighbour shell of MM atoms,

Those rules, according to our experience, allow performing stable MD simulations and optimizations with minimal user effort. It should be noted that, while for a simulation without link atoms the only required parameters for QM atoms are the VdW ones, here also bonded parameters are required.

III. COUPLING TO QM CODES

As explained in the previous section, OpenMMPol is a library which provides the polarizable MM quantities needed to assemble the QM/MMPol potential energy surface. To work, it needs to be interfaced with a QM software which acts as the driver.

In this section we show how to couple the OpenMMPol library to an existing QM code. As an example, we use the popular software PySCF.^{48,49} Alongside with the presentation of the interface we also provide some guidelines that can be helpful when interfacing a new software to the library. In particular, we start by describing how to couple OpenMMPol to a Hartree-Fock Self-Consistent Field (HF-SCF) code. To keep the notation simple, we limit the discussion to the HF case, but the generalization to Kohn-Sham density functional theory (DFT) is straightforward.

A. SCF Methods

Introducing an atomic orbital (AO) basis, the SCF generalized eigenvalue problem to be solved is

$$\mathbf{FC} = \mathbf{SC}\varepsilon, \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the Fock matrix, \mathbf{C} are the molecular orbital (MO) coefficients, ε is a diagonal matrix holding MO energies, and \mathbf{S} is the AO overlap matrix. The Fock matrix contains new terms due to the interaction between the QM subsystem and the MM fixed multipoles and induced dipoles:

$$F_{\mu\nu} = h_{\mu\nu} + h_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}} + G_{\mu\nu}(\mathbf{P}) + G_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}}(\mathbf{P}), \quad (15)$$

where the density-dependent term $G_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}}(\mathbf{P})$ describes the interaction of QM density with induced dipoles, and the density-independent $h_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}}$ for the one with fixed multipoles. These two terms read:

$$h_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}} = \sum_i^{\text{MM}} \sum_{L_1} (-1)^{L_1} M_i^{L_1} \langle \chi_\mu | \hat{t}_i^{L_1} | \chi_\nu \rangle, \quad (16)$$

$$G_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}}(\mathbf{P}) = - \sum_i^{\text{MM}} \mu_i(\mathbf{P}) \langle \chi_\mu | \hat{t}_i^1 | \chi_\nu \rangle, \quad (17)$$

the operator \hat{t}_i^L being

$$\hat{t}_i^L = \frac{\partial^L}{\partial r_i^\alpha \partial r_i^\beta \dots |r - r_i|}; \quad (18)$$

we remind here that $L_1 = 0$ for AMBER, while $L_1 = 0, 1, 2$ for AMOEBA which contains up to fixed quadrupoles. When AMOEBA is considered, attention should also be paid to the induced dipoles used in Eq. (17) which are the average of μ^d and μ^p (*cf.* Eq. (9)).

IPDs in Eq. (17) are computed according to Eq. (7), and therefore they depend on the electric field generated by the QM electronic density, here represented by the density matrix \mathbf{P} . This shows the mutual coupling between the QM and MM subsystems; in HF (and DFT) this mutual dependency can be easily addressed within the SCF iterative framework. At each SCF cycle the electric field generated by the current electronic density at polarizable sites is computed, the linear system (*cf.* Eq. (7)) is solved, and finally the interaction matrix in the AO basis (that is, last term of Eq. (17)) is computed and added to the Fock matrix. All the other terms do not present any further complication as they are exactly the same as in standard electrostatic embedding coupling.

To get the interface with the QM code working, it is necessary to alter the definition of the Fock matrix according to Eqs. (15)–(17). To maintain the logic of standard SCF, and to avoid double calculations, it is convenient to spot several regions of the code where the modification will be introduced (see Fig. 1). When the QM code computes the repulsion between nuclei, it should add the interaction between nuclei and MM charges (or the fixed multipoles, for AMOEBA) computed as dot product between `ommp_qm_helper%V.m2n` and the nuclear charges. Here other density-independent energy terms can be computed and added: bonded interactions, vdW interactions, MM electrostatic interactions except the ones with the induced dipoles. In PySCF we overloaded the function `energy_nuc`. Moreover, when the QM code computes the “core Hamiltonian”, the effect of the MM charges (or the fixed multipoles, for AMOEBA) should be added (Eq. (16)). Depending on the size of the system it could be convenient to compute the resulting atomic integrals on the fly or to store them in memory. In PySCF we overloaded the function `get_hcore`. Finally, when the QM code assembles the Fock matrix at each SCF iteration, it should also add the non-linear component that characterizes the polarizable embedding (Eq. (17)); to do so several steps are required:

1. the electric field \mathbf{E}^{QM} generated by the current QM electron density at the MM sites

is computed;

2. the electric field is fed to OpenMMPol via `set_external_field`; note that this field should also account for the nuclear charges of the QM subsystem. This triggers the solution of the linear system inside OpenMMPol.
3. the induced dipoles are retrieved from the MMPol Object via `ommp_system%ipd` and used to compute the polarization contribution to the Fock matrix (Eq. 17) and to the energy.

In PySCF we overloaded the function `get_veff`.

The overall result is that at each SCF cycle an updated linear system is solved, and new IPDs are computed. In our experience, this procedure does not deteriorate the convergence of the SCF algorithm if a tight enough convergence of the polarization equations is enforced. We also notice that during each SCF cycle the electric field integrals are used twice (once for computing the density's electric field and once to compute $G_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}}$); it is therefore convenient, unless very fast integrals routines are available, to store those integrals in memory during the whole SCF procedure.

As a general remark, when interfacing with a new code it is generally a good idea to proceed step-by-step going from trivial cases (*e.g.* simple electrostatic embedding without polarizabilities) to intermediate ones (*e.g.* MMPol) to reach the most difficult ones (*e.g.* AMOEBA). When trying to implement some method for which there is no reference available, it could be a good idea to compare the analytical Fock matrix, with a numerical one obtained computing the numerical derivative of the energy with respect to a small variation of the density matrix.

As a result of the SCF cycle, the QM/MM interaction energy reads

$$\mathcal{E}^{\text{QM/MM}} = \sum_{\mu\nu} P_{\mu\nu} h_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\mu\nu} P_{\mu\nu} G_{\mu\nu}^{\text{MMPol}}(\mathbf{P}) + \sum_i^{\text{QM}} \sum_j^{\text{MM}} Z_i \left(\sum_{L_1} T_{i,j}^{0L_1} M_i^{L_1} - \frac{1}{2} T_{ij}^{01} \mu_i(\mathbf{P}) \right), \quad (19)$$

which, together with the QM and purely MM energy, gives the total energy. Note that, as the QM/MM vdW contribution does not depend on the electronic density, we have implicitly included them in the MM energy.

FIG. 1. Graphical representation of the interface between OpenMMPol and PySCF. Note that the diagonalization of Fock matrix and the machinery of the self-consistent field is left untouched except for the extra terms added to the electronic energy and to the Fock matrix.

B. Forces

Gradients of the QM/MM energy with respect to the atomic coordinates are a fundamental tool as they enable molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and geometry optimizations. Analytical expressions for gradients are easily obtained from the QM/MM energy reported in the previous section. Starting from gradients with respect to MM coordinates, we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{E}}{\partial r_{k,MM}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{MM}}{\partial r_{k,MM}} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{QM}}{\partial r_{k,MM}} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{QM/MM}}{\partial r_{k,MM}} \quad (20)$$

where the $\frac{\partial}{\partial r_{k,MM}}$ denotes the partial derivative with respect to a specific coordinate of the k -th MM atom. The first term in Eq. (20) corresponds to the derivative of the MM energy

(including VdW interaction between QM and MM atoms) and it can be easily computed as the MM energy function is in a closed analytical form (see for example Eq.(3) for the electrostatic component). The second term vanishes and the last term can be obtained by differentiating the QM/MM interaction energy Eq.(19). The fixed electrostatic and polarization contributions are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{\text{QM/MM}}}{\partial r_{k,\text{MM}}} &= \sum_L M_k^L \sum_{\mu\nu} P_{\mu\nu} \langle \chi_\mu | \hat{t}_k^{L+1} | \chi_\nu \rangle \\ &\quad - \mu_k \cdot \sum_{\mu\nu} P_{\mu\nu} \langle \chi_\mu | \hat{t}_k^2 | \chi_\nu \rangle \\ &\quad + \sum_i^{\text{QM}} Z_i \left(\sum_L T_{i,k}^{1L} M_k^L - T_{i,k}^{11} \mu_k \right); \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

as noticed for Eq. 17, when AMOEBA is considered, μ_k is the average of μ^d and μ^p .

Gradients with respect to QM coordinates are computed similarly:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{E}}{\partial r_{\text{QM}}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{\text{MM}}}{\partial r_{\text{QM}}} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{\text{QM}}}{\partial r_{\text{QM}}} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{\text{QM/MM}}}{\partial r_{\text{QM}}} \quad (22)$$

where the first term reduces to the component on QM atoms of QM-MM vdW interaction, and the second is the standard geometric derivative of the SCF energy. The last term is again computed explicitly from the energy Eq. 19:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{E}^{\text{QM/MM}}}{\partial r_{i,\text{QM}}} &= \sum_k \sum_L M_k^L \sum_{\mu,\nu} P_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_{i,\text{QM}}} \langle \chi_\mu | \hat{t}_k^L | \chi_\nu \rangle \\ &\quad - \sum_k \mu_k \sum_{\mu,\nu} P_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial}{\partial r_{i,\text{QM}}} \langle \chi_\mu | \hat{t}_k^L | \chi_\nu \rangle \\ &\quad + \sum_k^{\text{MM}} Z_i \left(\sum_L T_{i,k}^{1L} M_k^L - T_{i,k}^{11} \mu_k \right) \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

It is useful to underline that all the quantities needed to compute the analytical MMPol-SCF gradients are one-electron integrals contracted with the QM density matrix and the proper electrostatic feature. Moreover, all those integrals (up to arbitrary order) could be efficiently evaluated using PRISM⁵⁰ or similar algorithms as three-center two-electron integrals (see Section I of the Supplementary Material for further details).

From a practical point of view, when an SCF code is interfaced with OpenMMPol, the forces on QM atoms should be modified in order to include the terms in Eq. 23; the calculation of first two terms should be inside the QM code, as they are simple contraction of

AO integrals that are computed with highly efficient generic matrix-matrix library function (eg. `dgemm`); the last term can be computed exploiting the `qm_helper` object, which is able to compute the required derivatives of QM nuclei electrostatic potential. Two density independent terms should also be added: the one corresponding to the QM-MM vdW force, and the one due to link-atoms; both of them are easily computed with OpenMMpol calling `ommp_qm_helper_vdw_geomgrad` and `ommp_qm_helper_link_atom_geomgrad` respectively.

The forces on MM atoms should also be computed inside the host code, following Eq. 20. All the purely MM components are easily computed inside the library calling the routine `ommp_full_geomgrad` (which is in turn a shorthand for calling `ommp_full_bnd_geomgrad`, `ommp_polelec_geomgrad`, `ommp_fixedelec_geomgrad` and `ommp_vdw_geomgrad`); the MM components of QM/MM vdW and link-atoms forces are computed by the same routine named for the corresponding QM components. All the terms from the QM/MM electrostatic coupling in Eq. 21 are computed inside the QM code in a way that closely resembles the one described for Eq. 23. If AMOEBA is used a last additional term should be added as a consequence of multipole rotation described in Section II B. This term is often called torque force across the literature and it basically describes the force needed to reorient an atom with an anisotropic electrostatic potential inside the constant field generated by the other atoms and the QM density. The derivation of this terms can be found in ref. 39. Here it suffices to say that it can be computed by the library, using the function `ommp_rotation_geomgrad` which requires the QM density's electric field and electric field gradient.

C. Electronic excitations

In the context of time-dependent (TD) HF and DFT, excitation energies and the corresponding transition moments are customarily obtained as poles and residues of the linear-response (LR) function, respectively.⁵¹ In practice, a generalized eigenvalue system of equations, known as Casida equations, needs to be solved. When real-valued orbitals are used, it assumes the following form

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{A}} & \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{B}} & \tilde{\mathbf{A}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{X}_K \\ \mathbf{Y}_K \end{pmatrix} = \omega_K \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{1} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{X}_K \\ \mathbf{Y}_K \end{pmatrix}, \quad (24)$$

ω_K being the K -th transition energy, and \mathbf{X}_K and \mathbf{Y}_K transition densities. The structure of the $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$ orbital rotation Hessian matrices is modified with respect to their usual form

by the addition of a polarization term $\mathcal{V}_{ai,bj}^{\text{pol}}$ directly influencing the system's response

$$\mathcal{V}_{ai,bj}^{\text{pol}} = - \sum_k^{N_{\text{pol}}} E_{ai}(\mathbf{r}_k) \mu_p^T(\phi_b \phi_j), \quad (25)$$

whose expression is the second derivative of the polarization Lagrangian with respect to the elements of the electronic density. $\boldsymbol{\mu}^T$ is the dipole induced by the electric field generated by the transition density element $\phi_b(\mathbf{r})\phi_j(\mathbf{r})$, and $E_{ai}(\mathbf{r}_k)$ is the field computed at the k -th polarizable site arising from $\phi_a(\mathbf{r})\phi_i(\mathbf{r})$. Also, we note that the molecular orbitals $\phi(\mathbf{r})$ and their energies stem from the solution of the modified SCF problem described in the previous section. The generalized eigenvalue problem and the polarization equation for $\boldsymbol{\mu}^T$ are solved iteratively in a self-consistent scheme.

This LR approach accounts only for a component of the response of the polarizable embedding, namely the one represented by the IDPs generated by the QM transition density. A second component instead should be computed by considering the IDPs generated by the change in the QM state density. In the literature, the former component is generally indicated as LR and the latter one as state-specific (SS). To recover the SS component in a LR formulations such as TDDFT, various models have been proposed.⁵²⁻⁵⁴ Here, we present the one that is more commonly used, e.g. the so-called corrected-LR (cLR)⁵² approximation. Within this framework, a correction to the excitation energy is computed according to the following expression:

$$\Delta\omega_K^{\text{cLR}} = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_k^{N_{\text{pol}}} \mu_k(\mathbf{P}_K^\Delta) E_k(\mathbf{P}_K^\Delta), \quad (26)$$

where \mathbf{P}_K^Δ is the change in the density matrix from the ground state to the excited state K . The latter requires solving the so called Z-vector equations.⁵⁵⁻⁵⁷ Finally, the cLR correction (26) can be directly added to the solution to the Eq. (24); this protocol was recently called cLR².⁵⁸

Practically, the OpenMMPol extension to the TDHF/TDDFT level of theory in PySCF only required overloading the function `gen_response` by adding the contribution given by Eq. (25). More specifically, at each iteration of the Davidson solver the electric field stemming from the transition density matrix is computed and the polarization equation is solved. Note that the nuclear contribution to the electric field should be discarded: this can be specified by setting to `True` the optional argument `exclude_nuclei` of the function

`set_external_field`. We finally note that, in the present implementation, the cLR correction (eq. 26) is still not available as OpenMMPol has not been coupled to Z-vector equations in PySCF.

IV. RESULTS

In this Section we report an in-depth analysis of the performance of the library and of the interface code that allows to perform SCF calculations using PySCF. All the tests have been performed on a single compute node equipped with two AMD EPYC 7282 processors (32 cores with multi-threading enabled) and 250 Gb of RAM. OpenMMPol was compiled with the Intel compiler v. 2023.1 using the `RELEASE` flags provided in the build system. PySCF was compiled with the GNU 12 compiler with the default option of the build system; both the codes are linked against the Intel MKL linear algebra libraries.

To test the performance of the library itself, we used a simple application that performs an initialization from a Tinker `.xyz` and `.prm` parameter file, computes all the electrostatic/polarization, bonded, and vdW contributions to the energy and the corresponding geometrical gradients reporting timings for each operation.

First, we benchmarked the performance of our parallel implementation. To this end we performed a fully MM calculation on the *Nudaurelia capensis* ω virus capsid protein⁵⁹ (PDB: 1OHF, see Figure 2B) composed of 35 695 polarizable atoms with the AMOEBA force field, using from 1 to 30 processors. We note that, since the MM operations performed by the library are the same as in a QM/MM calculation, the results and conclusions drawn here remain valid also for the latter case.

Results are shown in Figure 2. It can be seen that our library shows a very nice overall scaling, almost perfectly adhering to the ideal trend. The only part of the code that does not have a good scaling is the initialization. After investigation, it is clear that for systems with less than ~ 10 k atoms, the “constant” part of the initialization (*e.g.* parameter file parsing) is the most important one (see Fig. 3); unfortunately this part is not easily parallelizable, and the situation cannot be significantly improved without a complete strategy change. For systems with more than 100k atoms, the system-dependent part (which can be to some extent parallelized, see Fig. 3) becomes predominant, and the computational cost exhibits a nice linear scaling trend in the system size and a better scaling with respect to the number of

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PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0198251

FIG. 2. Results of parallelization performance tests performed on 1OHF. (A) Speed-up vs number of processor curve; the ideal speedup is indicated with the dashed red line, curves of the major contribution are depicted according to the legend and the total scaling is shown in black. (B) Representation of the simulated protein assembly (1OHF). (C,D) Major CPU time contribution of the calculation when running with 1 CPU (C) and with 30 CPUs (D).

CPUs. It should be anyway underlined that the initialization for systems of less than 100k atoms is pretty fast (requiring less than 1 s on our test node), and it is done only once per simulation (while the polarization routine is repeated every SCF cycle and all other terms are computed at each geometry change). In this sense the situation depicted in Fig. 2C is a worst-case scenario. Since all the other components have an almost ideal scaling, analyzing either panel B or C of Fig. 2 allows us to draw the same conclusions. For the system under analysis, all the time-consuming parts of the calculations are electrostatic-related, and the solution of the linear system in particular accounts for almost $2/3$ of the whole execution time. This is not surprising as in our code electrostatics is computed with a naïve double loop strategy, which proves here its shortcomings.

We have also performed a similar test, using a whole compute node, to compute energy and gradients of various proteins with sizes ranging from a few hundred to about 200 000

atoms. As before, the calculations are fully MM and they are obtained using AMOEBA force field. Results are reported in Fig. 3. It is clear from these data that every part of the

FIG. 3. Time spent in different parts of the code for proteins of different size. We have always computed vdW interactions with a 12 Å cutoff and initialized the system from Tinker's .xyz and .prm files. Results are shown in a log/log graph and ideal linear scaling trends at each order of magnitude are reported as red dashed lines.

code, excluding electrostatics, has the ideal linear-trend scaling. Electrostatic contributions instead show, as expected, a $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ scaling. As a consequence for every system with more than 1k atoms, the electrostatics becomes almost the only relevant part of the calculation, and all the other contributions are negligible with respect to it. This sub-optimal scaling also sets the current upper bound to the size of tractable systems on an average compute node between 10k and 100k polarizable atoms. This problem can however be tackled using a fast multipoles method algorithm to obtain a linear-scaling computational cost in the system's size for any required numerical accuracy.

One of the most important strengths of the OpenMMPol library is its ability to compute the full potential energy (i.e. electrostatics, polarization, bonded and VdW terms), and its geometrical gradients. Thanks to this feature, OpenMMPol-PySCF interface is able to perform QM/MMPol MD simulations and geometry optimizations.

To demonstrate the MD capabilities, we report here a short trajectory of a model system. The chosen system is alanine dipeptide solvated with explicit water (see Figure 4B): the system comprises 9876 polarizable atoms (3292 water molecules) and 22 QM atoms (alanine dipeptide). The MM part is described with AMOEBA while the QM part with B3LYP/6-31G (114 basis functions). The simulation is run at constant energy, without any boundary

condition. These open boundary conditions can only be used for very short dynamics when a large buffer of water molecules is around the system. For longer trajectories, since periodic boundary conditions have not been implemented yet for QM/MMPol models, one can use a large layer of ‘frozen’ solvent molecules around the system.⁶⁰ A three-layer approach coupling QM, MMpol and an external continuum model has also been used in the literature,⁶¹ and we plan to implement this feature in the library soon.

The initial configuration is taken from the last frame of a short constant temperature simulation, used to relax the system on the desired potential energy surface. The trajectory was propagated with the internal velocity Verlet integrator available in PySCF. Figure 4A

FIG. 4. Results of the MD trajectory performed on a solvated alanine dipeptide. (A) Energy change (Kcal/mol) during the trajectory. (B) Representation of the simulated system.

shows that the energy is conserved during the MD simulation, and no drift is observed, meaning that the energy and the gradients are well consistent.

To further investigate the computational efficiency and bottlenecks of the QM-MMpol terms, we have performed and profiled a QM/AMOEBA energy and gradient calculation on the DRONPA Green Fluorescent Protein⁶², solvated in explicit water, as already prepared in a previous paper by our group.⁶¹ Here the system is composed by 14578 polarizable atoms, and a QM part, treated with B3LYP/6-31g(d), with 466 basis functions (see Figure 5C).

From Figure 5A it is clear that the main bottlenecks in the current implementation are in the solution of the linear system and in the calculation of the core Hamiltonian. This is something completely expected; the first operation, performed on a pretty large system as the one used in this example, suffers from the non-optimal $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ scaling in computing electrostatic interactions we have already commented. The calculation of the core Hamiltonian is done contracting atomic orbital integrals with the static multipoles and

FIG. 5. (A) Timing for a QM/AMOEBA energy and gradient calculation performed with PySCF interfaced with OpenMMPol. To keep the diagram clear, all the steps that are below 5% of total execution are neglected, and summed under “Other”. Times are expressed in seconds. (B) Timing for the calculation of the derivatives of QM-MM couplings (see Eq. 21 and Eq. 23). (C) Speedup vs number of CPU curves for the different steps of the SCF calculation analyzed in panel A, and for the total calculation time (in black). (D) Graphical representation of the solvated DRONPA protein used for the benchmark; the QM region (excluding the link atoms) is represented in the zoom.

is basically limited by the computation of the integrals themselves. A substantial speedup in the SCF cycle was attained by storing the electric field integrals in memory and neglecting all the elements close to zero (this, especially for large molecules/basis sets, saves a considerable amount of memory). In this way the calculation of the QM electric field, needed to assemble the RHS of eq. 7 and the contribution to the Fock matrix (eq. 17) at each SCF cycle does not require to recalculate the large array of atomic orbital integrals.

Almost half of the calculation time is dedicated to computing forces on QM and MM atoms and, once more, the calculation of an even larger number (with respect to SCF core

Hamiltonian) of integrals is the main bottleneck (see Fig. 5B), together with their contraction with multipoles. In the evaluation of these results, it should be considered that the integrals for computing high order derivatives of the electric field are written with a code generator, and are likely not fully optimized. As a matter of fact, while in the energy the largest overhead is actually due to the polarization (namely the solution of the linear system), for the forces, the overhead is due to the large number of static dipoles and quadrupoles. For an AMBER-like formulation, where only fixed charges are needed, the overall cost for the same system would be greatly reduced.

In Figure 5C the parallel performances are analyzed. Overall we notice that, while the scaling is not optimal, it is still good. The parts of the code that exhibit a lower scaling are the calculations of QM/AMOEBA interactions which, as pointed out before, are basically calculation and contraction of atomic integrals with density matrices or electrostatic multipoles. Since the contraction operation is performed with the highly parallel optimized `dgemm` routine from BLAS library, we can speculate that the suboptimal scaling observed in those part of the code can be ascribed to the integral calculations which is expected to be suboptimal for the reasons mentioned above.

V. SUMMARY

We have presented the OpenMMPol library that can be used in combination with QM codes to run polarizable QM/MM calculations of energies, electronic excitations, geometry optimizations and dynamics of complex systems. OpenMMPol is the first library implementation which is able to compute QM/MM energies and gradients also including the fully MM terms of the potential. Despite the low computational cost of those terms, this feature should not be overlooked, as it allows to perform geometry optimization and MD without the need of any interface to external programs to compute the classical interactions. Even though our focus is mainly on polarizable QM/MM, we underline that also non-polarizable models are completely supported, and therefore once the interface is in operation it could also be used to perform e.g. electrostatic-embedding QM/AMBER calculations.

The OpenMMPol library is released with a permissive FOSS license and is completely agnostic with respect to the specific QM software and method. The modern build system adopted, and the overall clear and simple programming style of the source code, and its

flexibility, make it easy to use this library as a platform for further developments and experimentation of new algorithms. As a demonstration, and as a tutorial-code, we have presented an interface with the popular PySCF code for performing QM/AMOEBA calculations at HF, DFT (with gradients) and TD-DFT levels. The library will also allow to expand the number of methods interfaced with powerful polarizable QM/MM environment. In particular, we are currently working on interfacing the library to multiconfigurational SCF codes, in order to explore non-adiabatic dynamics methods.

As a final remark we want to underline that a great attention was paid to the computational efficiency and the parallel scalability of our code. To this end the main limiting factor is the quadratically scaling electrostatics which makes calculations with more than 100k atoms unpractical. To extend even further the field of application, in the near future a new version of the library implementing FMM methods for solving the electrostatics will be released.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Derivation of integrals needed for QM-AMOEBA and QM-MMPol coupling and derivative in term of 3-centers-2-electron integrals (also expressed as `libcint` functions); Description of `.mmp` legacy format.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

All authors acknowledge financial support from ICSC-Centro Nazionale di Ricerca in High Performance Computing, Big Data, and Quantum Computing, funded by the European Union – Next Generation EU – PNRR, Missione 4 Componente 2 Investimento 1.4. M.B. and B.M. gratefully acknowledge funding from the European Research Council under grant ERC-AdG-786714 (LIFETimeS). M.B. acknowledges the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high-performance computing resources and support (OMMPPOO).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The input files for the systems used for the tests and benchmarks presented in the present paper are provided together with the OpenMMPol code in the `tests` directory of the git repository.

CODE AVAILABILITY

OpenMMPol is released on GitHub and can be downloaded from <https://github.com/Molecolab-Pisa/OpenMMPol>; the version used in the present paper is 1.0.0.

The interface with PySCF is also provided on GitHub and can be downloaded from <https://github.com/Molecolab-Pisa/pyscf-openmmpol> (commit `fb2a75f`).

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PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0198251

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